

Tech transfer or co-innovation: communicating weather forecast for irrigation management

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Abstract

Irrigation in many regions of New Zealand can be managed using a better understanding of rainfall. However, access to reliable rainfall forecasts and the lack of understanding of current irrigation demands preclude many farmers from making informed irrigation decisions. A pilot study that combined current irrigation demands and short-term (2-6 day) rainfall forecast to enable informed irrigation decisions was conducted in a South Island river-based irrigation scheme. Pilot study farmers were provided near-real time access to on-farm measured soil moisture and region-specific weather forecasts. Water use efficiency was described as absence of irrigation-induced drainage below root zone. Initial results indicated that farmers used weather forecast for irrigation scheduling during shoulder season (Sep-Oct, Mar-Apr) but less so during peak season (Nov-Feb). Because of the potential unreliability of river supplies, farmers tend to practice a “just-in-case” approach where irrigations are scheduled around availability of river supply rather than crop demand and forecast rainfall. To enable the better uptake of weather forecasts for irrigation management, a combination of increasing the reliability of the water supply and accessibility of reliable weather forecasts, are necessary. While a tech transfer approach may enable hydrological and technological changes to irrigation management, our study also highlighted that to achieve a behaviour change, it is important to include collaboration, co-innovation and co-learning of irrigation management.

Background

In New Zealand, 70% of consumptive water use is consented for irrigation use. Two-thirds of irrigated areas are located in Canterbury (IrrigationNZ, 2017a). Since the late 1970's irrigated NZ farmland has doubled in area every 12 years (IrrigationNZ, 2017b), and the majority of the expansion has occurred in Canterbury. While irrigation has considerably increased the farm-gate revenue (New Zealand Institute of Economic Research, 2014), the strain on natural resources, especially on water, has been enormous as has been highlighted in several recent reports (e.g., Parliamentary Commissioner for the Environment, 2014; Environment Canterbury, 2016a; NIWA, 2017).

In response, central and local governments have devised various measures to keep water use and water quality under control. For instance, the NZ Ministry for the Environment has introduced several water policy statements and water quantity and quality reporting measures (e.g., Freshwater Management Reforms, National Policy Statement for Freshwater Management, Regulations for measurement and reporting of water takes, specifically targeting irrigation takes) and freshwater clean-up and protection projects (Ministry for the Environment, 2017). Regional governments such as Environment Canterbury have been working closely with agricultural industry in devising on-farm management practices that would result in better water and nutrient management practices and reduced spill of excess water and nutrients into ground and surface waters (Environment Canterbury, 2016b).

In Canterbury, a significant proportion of irrigation is derived from alpine rivers. A report published by Environment Canterbury indicates that major irrigation schemes (irrigated areas > 500 ha) in the region are 100% reliant on surface water and use as much as 60% of surface water is allocated in the region (Dommissive, 2004). Since abstraction consent conditions are commonly tied to river flows, many schemes face issues with supply reliability. Farmers in response to poor reliability, tend to practice a “just-in-case” approach to irrigation, where irrigations are applied whenever supplies are available. This often results in over-irrigation that leads to drainage, leaching and runoff. Farmers are advised to apply irrigation based on crop demand (“just-in-time”, or deficit irrigation) but the uptake of this message is still poor.

Srinivasan et al. (2017) discussed the practices of just-in-case and just-in-time and the need for better integration of irrigation supply and demand. In an effort to demonstrate the value of integrating short-

term rainfall forecast (supply) with current irrigation demand, we initiated a pilot study in a river-based irrigation scheme in Canterbury. The objectives of the pilot study were to (1) co-develop an irrigation scheduling strategy that combines current demand and supply as well as the use of short-term weather forecast; and (2) identify barriers and opportunities in advancing the proposed irrigation strategy among irrigators. The focus of the irrigation strategy was to improve water use efficiency by scheduling irrigation around current demand and supply and considering forecast rainfall. A co-innovation approach was used (Srinivasan et al., in review; Vereijssen et al., 2017; Srinivasan et al., 2017) to enhance the co-learning and co-development process during the pilot study. A description of the co-innovation approach used is available in Boyce et al. (2017).

Methods

The five-year water use efficiency pilot project started in October 2012 was based at the Waimakariri Irrigation scheme, a run-of-the-river irrigation scheme. The Waimakariri River is the main source of irrigation, and whenever river flows at the consent monitoring location, approximately 50 km downstream of abstraction point, fall below 63,000 Ls-1, then irrigation abstractions are to be reduced. All abstractions have to cease, when flow at the consent location drops below 41,000 Ls-1. The irrigation scheme often undergoes restrictions from January to March, the peak irrigation season. Thus the irrigation practices in the scheme are strongly influenced by the reliability of river flows which are currently at about 74% (Walton, 2015; WIS Executive Manager; personal communication).

The pilot was based on the premise that proactive irrigation management that matches current irrigation demands against forecasted (2-6 days) rainfall would lead to positive economic and environmental outcomes to farmers and wider society. The pilot was seen as a precision agriculture practice, where irrigation supplies and demands are matched in time.

Within the scheme, five farms were chosen and each farm instrumented with a rain gauge to measure both irrigation and rainfall and a soil moisture sensor to record soil moisture and soil temperature. Soil moisture was used as a proxy to demand. All on-farm data were collected at 10 minute intervals and telemetered to NIWA in near-real time. In addition, drainage data from in scheme drainage lysimeters, and weather data from a compact AgMet weather station installed in one of the pilot farms, were also used to further infer the efficiency of irrigation practice. Potential evaporation (Priestly-Taylor) was calculated from the weather data.

All pilot study farmers were given access to the raw data via a password-protected website. Also, a customised daily plot of the data was emailed to all farmers. This plot included the last seven days of measured soil moisture, rainfall and irrigation, and drainage, the estimated potential evaporation, and next 2 to 6 day weather forecast. While farmers were not provided advice on irrigation scheduling itself, the daily plots and on-line data access were designed to enable them to schedule irrigations based on supply and demand.

To encourage a collective approach, education and information sharing among farmers, all study farmers were provided access to data from all pilot farms, which enabled them to compare their conditions and practices against others as well as make useful observations of others' irrigation practices. The co-innovation approach allowed farmers to reflect on their practices. To enhance the co-innovation experience, an annual workshop reviewing irrigation data and practices was held with all farmers as a group. These workshops were used as forums to discuss the rationale behind farm irrigation practices and barriers to uptake of water management tools.

Results

Rainfall, irrigation and drainage data from one of the irrigation season (2014-15) were analysed in detail to decipher drainage from rainfall and irrigation. The lysimeters installed under irrigator recorded both rainfall and irrigation drainage. Whenever an irrigation event resulted in drainage, then it was considered a poor irrigation practice. During the season we examined, generally very few drainage events were observed during shoulder season (shoulder season, September-October and March-April; see Table 1 and Figure 1). However, during peak season (November to February), both irrigation and rainfall events resulted in more drainage than during the shoulder season. A closer analyses of two irrigation events (events A and B, Figures 2 and 3, respectively), indicated that if irrigation events scheduled carefully could have prevented drainage. This could have been achieved by either reducing the amount of irrigation applied, leaving space for rainfall, or delaying the irrigation so that the pasture can make use of rainfall.

Table 1. Summary of rainfall, irrigation, evaporation and drainage during 2014-15 irrigation season at one of the pilot farms.

Total rainfall (mm)	Total irrigation (mm)	Total potential ET ¹ (mm)	Total drainage from rainfall (mm)	Total drainage from irrigation (mm)	Number of rain days	Number of irrigation days	Number of rainfall-drainage days	Number of irrigation-drainage days	Number of instances 2 mm, or more, rainfall recorded within a day of irrigation
Shoulder season (September, October, March, April); total, 153 days									
143.0	138.4	362.6	15.8	2.9	54	26	5	2	6
Peak season (November, December, January, February); total, 120 days									
107.6	317.8	587.2	19.1	62.3	40	64	16	25	14

¹ Potential ET is based on Priestly-Taylor method.

Figure 1. Rainfall, irrigation and drainage measured during 2014-15 irrigation season in one of the pilot farms of Waimakariri Irrigation Scheme. Further details on events A and B are shown in Figure 2 and 3 respectively

Figure 2. An irrigation event that was immediately followed by a rainfall event. Drainage resulted following the rainfall event. Measured data from one of the pilot farms in the Waimakariri Irrigation Scheme. Same colour scheme used as in Figure 1.

Figure 3. An irrigation event scheduled between two rainfall events yet resulting in no drainage. Measured data from one of the pilot farms in the Waimakariri Irrigation Scheme. Same colour scheme used as in Figure 1.

During the peak irrigation season, a decrease in rainfall and an increase in potential ET resulted in more irrigation events. However, the peak season also suffered from poor supply reliability, as river levels went below abstraction limits more often (data not shown). Compared to the shoulder season, during the peak season, irrigation applied was as much as three times that of rainfall recorded. However, potential ET during peak season was only 1.6 times that of shoulder season. Almost every 3 out of 5 irrigation events was either preceded or followed by 2 mm or more of rainfall. The irrigation drainage during peak season was 21 times that of shoulder season, while rainfall-drainage for that same period went up by 1.2 times. During peak season, as the number of irrigation days increased, so did the irrigation drainage. The study farm had a secondary source of irrigation (groundwater), thus had the opportunity to continue to irrigate even when the river was under restriction.

Discussion

Apart from hydrological considerations, generally a large drainage during peak season was indicative of two key behavioural attributes: (a) unlike shoulder season when supply reliability was almost 100% (river flows never falling below abstraction limits), the reliability was low during the peak season, encouraging farmers to irrigate whenever river supply was available, with no attention paid to rainfall forecast; (b) as irrigation events were primarily based on supplies, farmers did not take notice of demands, hence applied irrigation even when soil had little available capacity to hold irrigation. This was reflected in large drainage during peak season. Even a day of delay in irrigation could have resulted in less drainage than what was recorded.

Co-innovation workshops allowed farmers to reflect and reason out on their practices. While hindsight at the workshops offered farmers the time to think and realign their practices, the lack of supply reliability still inhibited a system change.

Conclusion

Use of weather forecast offers farmers in water limited regions provide an opportunity to better schedule irrigations. When irrigations are scheduled around rainfall forecasts, less drainage would generally result. During the peak irrigation season, when irrigation is scheduled based solely on available supplies, generally a large drainage was observed. The ability of farmers to integrate forecasts into irrigation practice is dependent on their reliability and timeliness, to enable informed decisions. The use of weather forecasting does present an opportunity for improving precision farming practices.

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